

Article

Coupling of integrated waveguide and optomechanic cavity for microwave phonon excitation in Si nanobeams

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Abstract: The availability of high quality manufacturing for optical micro/nano patterned cavities paves the way to the development of scalable circuits and devices based on optomechanical (OM) interaction of sound and light in extremely small volumes. In this contribution, we propose a new study on OM cavities, that can lead to precise control of their coupling with closely integrated waveguides, a necessary condition to enhance mode excitation and wave energy trapping, opening the possibility for many potential applications in wave guiding, filtering, confinement, and sensing. Moreover, in this way the need for bulky experimental setups and/or optical fiber coupling/excitation is avoided. At the same time, quality factors of mechanical and optical modes resonating in the cavity are optimized, together with their OM coupling coefficients: high confinement of both excitations is a prerequisite to enable their acousto-optic (AO) interaction. To this aim, the transversal size of the cavity has been parabolically tapered, with the additional benefit of separating the cavity and the integrated waveguide far from the coupling region. Finite-element method has been used to perform full-wave analysis, and an accurate discussion about the simulation setup needed to properly describe optical scattering and radiation has been provided.

Keywords: Opto mechanical interaction; Photonic cavity; Phononic cavity

1. Introduction

The purpose of a resonant optomechanical (OM) system [1][2][3] is to enhance the interaction of light with a mechanical oscillator, basing on light and acoustic wave confinement in the same photonic/phononic (often referred as "phoxonic") cavities [4][5][6][7][8][9][10][11][12], by means of high mechanical and optical Q resonances. Such cavities have been designed in phoxonic (or OM) crystals that exhibit simultaneous photonic and phononic band gaps [13][14][15]. Current research trends on OM structures include topics such as radiation-pressure cavity cooling [16][17], quantum coherent optomechanics [1][18], coherent amplification/cooling of Surface Acoustic Waves (SAWs) in optomechanical microcavities [19][20][21][22][23][24][25], and high resolution sensing, in particular of biomolecules [26][27][28]. The basic phonon circuits which are typically taken into consideration are resonant mechanical cavities, as promising building blocks of more complex devices, including filters, couplers, and mechanical sources/detectors. GHz phonons travelling in suspended nanobeams are good candidates as new state variable for signal transmission and processing in the microwave range of frequencies, owing to their small wavelength and radiationless propagation. The emerging field of OM cavities is expecting to enable on-chip photonic-operated phononic circuits [29]. Phoxonics promises

31 for a new mean of processing and transmitting signals at microscale; key enabling elements are the
32 currently available advanced nanofabrication techniques for highly spatially resolved microcavities,
33 and the evidence of self-oscillations/phonon lasing up to the GHz range. In addition, the mechanical
34 interaction between two OM cavities can be exploited for synchronization purpose. A demonstration
35 of such systems is provided in [30], where OM cavities, intercoupled by mechanical link, support
36 independent optical modes oscillating in antiphase, and can be temporarily de-synchronized by
37 actuating one of the cavities with a heating laser, so that both cavities oscillate independently. The
38 control of the mechanical interaction opens the way to the realization of distributed networks of OM
39 resonators, for a future technology platform, possibly CMOS compatible.

40 In this contribution, we provide a rigorous analysis of the optical coupling between an optical
41 integrated waveguide and a suspended Si nanobeam where a resonant cavity is patterned, namely
42 a quasi-periodic structure consisting in repeated holes and “wings” (lateral stubs) acting as periodic
43 loads for bandgap engineering [10][11]. We show how it is possible to improve the quality factor of
44 the OM cavity by proper tapering of the length of the lateral stubs, which, in turns, provide also an
45 additional degree of freedom to change the frequencies of the mechanical and optical modes. We focus,
46 by the present simulations, about the maximization of the strength and the efficiency of the optical
47 coupling between the cavity and the lateral integrated waveguide. Indeed, the excitation and detection
48 of the optical and mechanical cavity modes can be more efficiently controlled with such an integrated
49 waveguide than with an external tapered optical fiber[31][32]. To this aim, two main parameters are
50 being considered for optimization, namely (1) the distance between the waveguide and the cavity, and
51 (2) the position of a Bragg mirror patterned in the waveguide, with respect to the center of the resonant
52 cavity (see next section).

53 The work is organized as follows: the next Section reports the optimization of the coupling
54 between a uniform OM cavity and the closely placed uniform waveguide, with embedded optical
55 mirror, including calculation of the OM coupling coefficients in terms of photoelastic (PE) and moving
56 interface (MI) contributions [10][11][33]. We also show the improvements achievable by proper
57 modulation (parabolic tapering) of the geometrical parameters of the cavity. In the Discussion section,
58 device optimization and comparative analyses are performed. In Material and Methods, the unit cell of
59 the OM cavity has been characterized in terms of frequency dispersion and formation of band gaps at
60 prefixed frequencies, both for phononic and photonic modes, with reference to the specific symmetry
61 of the nanobeam. All simulation details are also provided in this section. Final considerations will
62 conclude the work.

63 2. Results

64 The considered structure and related simulation setup is constituted by two parallel suspended
65 Si nanobeams (see next subsections). The first nanobeam is a phoxonic one-dimensional crystal
66 with periodic holes and stubs, exhibiting simultaneous band gaps for photons in the range of
67 telecommunication wavelengths (1550nm or equivalently 193.5THz) and for phonons around 2GHz. It
68 is worth noticing that the holes and the stubs are respectively favorable for the opening of the photonic
69 and phononic band gaps [9][10][11] (see the dispersion curves of the crystal in Material and Methods
70 section). The middle of the phoxonic crystal hosts a resonant OM cavity created by a parabolic graded
71 variation of the holes and stubs sizes from the peripheries towards the center. The second nanobeam is
72 the waveguide carrying the injected incident light and is terminated by a tapered Bragg mirror made
73 of holes in order to stop the progression of light and keep it in the vicinity of the OM cavity. Two
74 main design parameters are considered to optimize the optical coupling and energy transfer from the
75 waveguide to the nanobeam cavity, namely the distance D between the waveguide and the cavity,
76 and the position of the Bragg mirror (measured from the center of its smaller hole) with respect to the
77 center of the resonant cavity, indicated by L_0 .

78 **2.1. Case of study 1: Cavity with fixed heights of the stubs**

79 In the perspective of integration of a structured nanobeam inside a phoXonic device, we start
 80 to investigate the efficiency of the photonic coupling between a uniform cavity (without tapering of
 81 the stub heights) and a Bragg mirror waveguide transporting an incident optical wave. This is one
 82 of the main objectives of this paper. We show in Fig. 1a represents the schematic view of the device
 83 where one can see the lateral waveguide terminated by the Bragg mirror. Figure 1b represents the
 84 unit cell of the perfect phoxonic crystal and its geometric parameters. In Fig. 1a, the number 0 is
 85 used to mean a common index for the elements (namely, five stubs and holes on the left side of the
 86 cavity with respect to its center, and, symmetrically, five of them on the right side) whose geometric
 87 parameters are constant and equal to each other. In total, the phoxonic crystal is defined by 26 holes
 88 (and corresponding stubs). The pitch, a_i , of the holes of radii r_i , is the same as the pitch of the i -th stub,
 89 whose length and width are indicated by h_i and w_i respectively. In the present case of a uniform cavity,
 90 all h_i are the same. The thickness of the nanobeams is $t=220$ nm, and their width is $w_0=500$ nm.
 91 It is noted that the optical signal is injected and collected by means of waveport excitation, with
 92 radiation boundaries assumed elsewhere: the objective is to optimize the transfer of the optical
 93 excitation wave from the incident waveguide to the cavity. In Table 1 we report the values of the
 94 geometrical parameters of the cavity.

Figure 1. (a) Geometry of the simulated uniform optical structure. Geometric parameters D (waveguide-cavity distance) and L_0 (mirror position) are shown. (b) Unit cell and geometric parameters of the unit cell in the perfect phoxonic crystal.

Table 1. Uniform cavity parameters

N cell	a_i (nm)	w_i (nm)	r_i (nm)
0	500	250	150
1	500	250	150
2	500	250	150
3	470.97	235.48	141.29
4	447.22	223.61	134.165
5	428.75	214.375	128.63
6	415.54	207.77	124.67
7	407.64	203.82	122.3
8	405	202.5	121.5

95 The efficiency of the coupling is based on the search of the maximum energy localized in the
 96 cavity, as a function of the parameters D and L_0 . In parallel, we need to keep low the transmission from
 97 the excited cavity towards both sides (ports 2 and 3 of Fig. 1a) of the phoxonic cavity, to reduce losses.
 98 The following quantities have been calculated: optical quality factor, optical scattering parameters
 99 at the excitation ports, and opto-mechanical (OM) coupling, by using two different methods, to
 100 assess numerical consistency (first-order perturbation method and direct simulation by COMSOL
 101 multiphysics). Starting with a phoxonic crystal without the lateral waveguide, the field distributions of
 102 three optical eigenmodes with highest quality factors have been calculated and the results are reported
 103 in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Maps of the optical cavity modes for the uniform OM cavity. Top pictures: E field magnitude, bottom pictures: real part of the E field components. Their imaginary parts are very small and not shown.

104 To illustrate the method for the optimization of the parameters D and L_0 , let us consider, for
 105 instance, the optical eigenmode located at the wavelength $\lambda = 1615$ nm, and chose $L_0 = -50$ nm. We
 106 expect that adding the lateral waveguide with Bragg mirror, and decreasing the distance D between
 107 the two waveguides, the values of the quality factor and the optical frequency of the photonic modes
 108 decrease owing to a higher coupling. The Bragg mirror is needed to maximize the electromagnetic (e.m.)
 109 transmission from the input waveguide to the cavity. Fig. 3 shows the optical transmission/reflection
 110 and e.m. energy density curves obtained. Concerning the optical transmission, the source of the e.m.
 111 wave is located at port 1, as defined in Fig. 1a, and the scattered waves are collected at all the four
 112 ports of the structure. With a unit input power, Fig. 3a presents the transmission T through ports
 113 2 or 3, the reflection R at port 1, as well as the radiated fraction of the power defined by $1-R-2T$
 114 for different distance values D - between 500 and 700 nm -, and assuming $L_0 = -50$ nm. Transmission at
 115 port 4 is almost zero. It can be noted that both the minimum reflection towards the input port 3 and
 116 the maximum of the radiated power are obtained for the same distance D around 550 nm. Fig. 3b
 117 shows the highest e.m. energy density in the phoxonic crystal cavity which also shows its maximum
 118 for the same distance $D = 550$ nm. This value of D defines the best coupling efficiency in terms of field
 119 strength in the cavity for the given value of L_0 . Now, the same operation needs to be repeated for
 120 different values of L_0 . Let us notice here that the phoxonic crystal must have a sufficient number of
 121 the perfect unit cells around the cavity in order to ensure a good confinement of the cavity mode and
 122 avoid leakage through ports 2 and 3.

Figure 3. E.m. simulation of the cavity-waveguide system. (a) Transmission towards ports 2 or 3 (dotted lines), reflection towards port 1 (full lines) and radiated fraction of the optical power (dashed lines) for $\lambda = 1615$ nm in the geometry of Fig. 1a. Transmission at port 4 is almost zero. (b) Energy density inside the cavity. The colors indicate the distance D between the phoxonic crystal and the optical waveguide while $L_0 = 50$ nm.

123 The remaining simulation steps involve the calculation of the OM coupling between the different
 124 detected photonic and phononic modes. It can be noted that the phoxonic structure has significant
 125 OM coupling rates between the three optical modes and two phononic ones located at $F_{\text{phon}} = 2.39$
 126 GHz and $F_{\text{phon}} = 2.43$ GHz. In the calculation of the OM coupling, we have taken into account both
 127 mechanisms of photoelastic (PE) and moving interface (MI) effects, and get efficient OM coupling
 128 rates, g_{OM} , ranging from 1 to 2 MHz. The mechanical displacement and the e.m. field distributions of
 129 these modes are shown in Fig. 4. The mechanical motions correspond to a breathing of the stubs close
 130 to the cavity center. It should be noticed that despite their strong coupling rates, these two resonant
 131 mechanical modes fall outside the frequency range of the band gap around 2 GHz. In order to produce
 132 a downwards shift of these modes towards the gap, we design in the next section another cavity with
 133 a gradual variation of the stubs heights.

Figure 4. Uniform cavity: optomechanical coupling with phonons around 2.4 GHz and maps of the phonon cavity modes. Both photoelastic (PE) and moving interface (MI) effects are considered.

134 2.2. Case of study 2: Phoxonic cavity with parabolic variations of the stub heights

135 A gradual variation of the stubs heights is needed in order not only to push the mechanical modes
 136 inside the phononic SS (symmetric-symmetric) band gap (see "Materials and Methods"), but also to
 137 improve the optical confinement and increase the resonant quality. In fact, the structured nanobeam
 138 cavity allows to get phononic modes working around 2.0 GHz and photonic ones at about 1.550 nm.
 139 We optimize the tapering rate over the lattice constants of the nanobeam and establish an excitation of
 140 the phononic/photonic cavity modes at the desired frequencies. The design of the tapered cavity has
 141 been done following a parabolic evolution of the elementary unit cell. Fig. 5a shows the final design of
 142 the cavity. **Figure 5b represents the unit cell of the perfect phoxonic crystal, and** Table 2 reports the
 143 corresponding geometrical parameters. Assuming such parameters we obtained the excitation of 2
 144 phononic modes closed to 2.0 GHz and 3 photonic modes closed to 1550 nm.

Figure 5. (a) Geometry of the OM cavity with tapered stub heights. (b) Unit cell and geometric parameters of the unit cell in the perfect phoxonic crystal.

Table 2. Tapered cavity parameters

N cell	h_i (nm)	a_i (nm)	w_i (nm)	r_i (nm)
0	500	500	250	150
1	500.08	500.17	250.085	150.51
2	550.06	460.13	230.065	138.04
3	592.9	425.81	212.905	127.74
4	628.6	397.21	198.605	119.16
5	657.16	374.33	187.165	112.29
6	678.58	357.27	178.64	107.18
7	692.9	347.735	172.9	103.72
8	700	340	170	102

145 Starting again with a phoxonic crystal without the lateral waveguide, for the case of parabolic
 146 tapering cavity, the field distributions of the three optical eigen modes with highest quality factors
 147 have been calculated: numerical results are reported in Fig. 6. In comparison to the previous cavity,
 148 one can notice a similarity in the shape of the optical modes although their frequencies are shifted and
 149 the order of the modes has been changed.

Figure 6. Maps of the optical cavity modes for the tapered OM cavity. Top pictures: E field magnitude, bottom pictures: real part of the E field components. Their imaginary parts are very small and not shown.

150 Finally, the OM coupling rates between the three optical modes and the three phononic ones
 151 located at $F_{\text{phon}} = 1.95, 2.002$ and 2.05 GHz have been reported in Fig. 7. The mechanical displacement
 152 and e.m. field distribution of the considered modes are shown in the same figure. The displacement
 153 fields mostly correspond to the motions of the stubs. Again, the coupling rates g_{OM} range between 0.5
 154 to 2 MHz.

Figure 7. Tapered cavity: optomechanical coupling with phonons around 2 GHz and maps of the phonon cavity modes. Both photoelastic (PE) and moving interface (MI) effects are considered.

155 3. Discussion

156 With reference to the optical scattering parameters and to the e.m. energy density in the cavities,
 157 we report a general view to the optical coupling calculations that was performed on the phoxonic
 158 crystal varying the geometric parameters D and $L0$. Fig. 8 and Fig. 9 show the results obtained for
 159 the uniform and tapered cavities, respectively. In order to estimate the best conditions for the optical
 160 coupling we need to take into account two main effects: the lower the distance D the better the
 161 coupling, but, consequently, the lower the quality factor Q of the cavity, due to optical leakage from
 162 the cavity to the waveguide. In general, an optimum distance D can be found. As shown in Fig. 8 and
 163 Fig. 9, the optimum distance changes for different values of $L0$. For the uniform cavity, and for the
 164 considered resonant mode taken as an example ($\lambda = 1615$ nm), the best condition in terms of field
 165 strength in the cavity is given by $L0 = -50$ nm, $D = 550$ nm; this allows us to achieve the highest e.m.
 166 energy density in the cavity and radiation power, and consequently the lowest reflection towards the
 167 input port, while maintaining a sufficiently high quality factor. Under these conditions, the energy
 168 density is $1.7 * 10^8$ J/m³, the quality factor is $Q = 4 * 10^5$, and the input reflection is about 0.0062.

Figure 8. Optimization of D and L_0 for the optical mode at $\lambda = 1615$ nm (uniform cavity).

169 For the case of cavity with parabolic tapering of the stub heights, the optimum conditions for D
 170 and L_0 have been also estimated as follows. For the considered resonant mode taken as an example
 171 ($\lambda = 1550$ nm), the best condition in terms of field strength in the cavity is given by $L_0 = 0$ nm, $D =$
 172 550 nm. In this case, the resulting energy density is $8 \times 10^9 J/m^3$, the input reflection is 0.0067, and the
 173 quality factor is $Q = 1.71 \times 10^7$.

Figure 9. Optimization of D and L_0 for the optical mode at $\lambda = 1550\text{nm}$ (tapered cavity).

174 The numerical results just obtained for uniform and parabolic OM cavities have been compared
 175 in Fig. 10. From this figure, one can note that the optimal parameters D and L_0 are different from one
 176 mode to another, Indeed, for the mode located at 1615 nm (resp. 1550 nm for the parabolic cavity) the
 177 optimal parameters are $D=550$ nm and $L_0=-50$ nm (resp. $D=550\text{nm}$ and $L_0=0$), whereas the optimal
 178 optical coupling of the mode located at 1598 nm (resp. 1540 nm for the parabolic cavity) is obtained
 179 for relatively greater distances of $D=650\text{nm}$ and $L_0=250\text{nm}$ (resp. $D=700$ nm and $L_0=250\text{nm}$). This
 180 difference can be explained from the spatial distribution of the electric field associated with each mode.
 181 Indeed, the electric field associated with the second mode penetrates more into the stubs and becomes
 182 closer to the waveguide transporting the incident field. By exploiting the additional degree of freedom
 183 given by the modulation of stub heights, we have achieved better quality factors and higher energy
 184 densities of the e.m. field excited in the cavities by the lateral waveguide.

Cavity with fixed heights of the stubs

	$\lambda=1598$ nm	$\lambda=1615$ nm
Optimal D and L0	D=650 nm; L0=250 nm	D=550 nm; L0=-50 nm
Quality factor	1.63×10^6	4×10^5
Energy density	5.22×10^8 J/m ³	17×10^7 J/m ³
Reflection	0.0082	0.0062

Cavity with parabolic variations of the stub heights

	$\lambda=1540$ nm	$\lambda=1550$ nm
Optimal D and L0	D=700 nm; L0=250 nm	D=550 nm; L0=0 nm
Quality factor	3.46×10^7	1.7×10^7
Energy density	16×10^9 J/m ³	8.4×10^9 J/m ³
Reflection	0.03	0.0067

Figure 10. Optical features of uniform and tapered cavities: comparison of numerical results.

185 **4. Materials and Methods**

186 In this section, we provide detailed definition of the phoxonic crystal and simulation setup
 187 used in numerical calculation. All simulations have been performed using finite element methods
 188 implemented by COMSOL multiphysics solver. The typical geometry under consideration, and related
 189 simulation setup, is shown in Fig. 11. Two suspended Si nanobeams are used to confine the optical
 190 signal at infrared frequency, and to host respectively a resonant OM cavity and a Bragg mirror. We
 191 varied the distance between the two nanoguides D and the position L_0 of the Bragg mirror with respect
 192 to the middle of the cavity to maximize their coupling. It is noted in Fig. 11 that the optical signal is
 193 injected and collected by means of wave-port excitation, with radiation boundaries, or alternatively
 194 perfect matched layers, assumed elsewhere.

Figure 11. Modelling setup: simulated optical structure.

195 A frequency dispersion characterization of the periodic cells was needed to obtain both optical
 196 and mechanical resonant modes in pre-defined bands. In order to increase the mechanical quality
 197 factor of OM cavities patterned in nanobeams, several strategies have been recently used [34], such as,
 198 for instance, uniform stress, soft-clamping, and geometric strain engineering. In the present work, we
 199 acted on stubs size and distribution across the beam length to modulate the resonant wavelength of
 200 the mechanical modes: specifically, increasing stub length and width usually produces an increase of
 201 the resonant wavelength. In this way, we place the mode resonances in the mechanical band gap of
 202 the periodic part of the cavity crystal, so that the quality factor is maximized. As mentioned above,
 203 the geometrical parameters of the phoxonic nanobeam are designed to obtain the optical resonances
 204 around 1550nm and the acoustic resonances around 2GHz. The latter is also a suitable choice to
 205 make easier an independent excitation of the acoustic cavity modes by means of SAW generated by
 206 interdigitated electrodes on a multilayer substrate in front of the nanobeam as shown in our recent
 207 work [24]. We show in Fig. 12 the dispersion curves for the mechanical (Fig. 12a) and optical (Fig. 12b)
 208 modes, related to the unit cell of Fig. 1b. The different branches are characterized according to their
 209 symmetry (S (symmetric) or A (anti-symmetric)) with respect to the two symmetry planes xOz and
 210 xOy of the structure. Only symmetric modes with respect to the xOy plane are presented whereas the
 211 red and blue colors refer to the S and A modes with respect to the xOz plane. It should be stressed that,
 212 based on symmetry consideration, only mechanical modes of SS symmetry can display an efficient
 213 OM coupling [10][11][33] as studied in the previous sections. In Fig. 12, one can notice a full photonic
 214 band gap below the light line of vacuum, represented by the gray shaded area. On the other hand,
 215 a band gap of SS symmetry is obtained for acoustic modes around 2 GHz. The optical and elastic
 216 properties used in the calculation are provided in Table 3, where C_{ij} are the elastic constants, P_{ij} are the
 217 photo-elastic coefficients, ρ is the mass density, and n is the refractive index.

Table 3. Optical, elastic and photoelastic properties of silicon

C11 (GPa)	C12 (GPa)	C44 (GPa)	ρ (kg/m ³)	P11	P12	P44	n
165.7	63.9	79.9	2330	-0.1	0.01	-0.051	3.5

Figure 12. (a) Phononic and (b) photonic dispersion curves. The red and blue branches respectively correspond to the Anti-symmetric (A) and Symmetric (S) modes with respect to the xOz plane. All the considered branches are Symmetric (S) with respect to the xOy plane. The shaded area corresponds to the bandgaps. The straight line in panel (b) is the light line in vacuum.

218 It is remarked that all simulations related to the complete structure (Fig. 11) have been performed
 219 with particular care to possible numerical issues, which are strongly amplified by the high Q resonance
 220 of the considered cavities:

- 221 - spatial mesh: changing any geometrical parameter means changing the mesh, then the numerical
 222 impact of changing the mesh must be minimized;
- 223 - radiating boundaries: even a small reflection from the radiating boundary could strongly impact the
 224 final results due the high Q of the cavity, so PML thickness and distance can become critical parameters.
 225 In order to overcome this issue, several tests have been made varying PML thickness and position,
 226 until consistent and repeatable results were obtained;
- 227 - e.m. excitation waveports: port size could be too small to correctly capture the slab guided mode, but
 228 ports cannot be made too large otherwise i) they overlap when reducing D and ii) they undesirably
 229 intercept radiated field. In general a good compromise for the port size is needed, and, anyway, other
 230 approaches are possible: the computational domain can be extended to allow proper calibration of the
 231 electromagnetic field excitation coming from the waveports.

232 5. Conclusions

233 In this work, we investigated the optomechanical interaction taking place in a corrugated phoxonic
 234 silicon nanobeam where periodic loads (stubs) and holes are designed to provide simultaneous
 235 bandgaps for photonic and phononic modes, and where an integrated waveguided is used to effectively
 236 excite mode resonances. Such a choice prevents from the need of an external fiber excitation, and
 237 contributes to the possibility of component integration, scalability, and circuit compactness. **With**
 238 **respect to the state of the art of OM cavities, we have introduced an additional parabolic taper of the**
 239 **periodic stubs of the involved photonic crystal, in order to:** (i) place the mechanical mode resonances
 240 in the mechanical band gap of the **periodic** crystal of the cavity, (ii) optimize the distance between
 241 the cavity and the integrated waveguided, and the position of the Bragg mirror patterned in the
 242 lateral waveguide, to allow maximum e.m. field transfer to the cavity, (iii) ensure a proper spacing

243 between the lateral integrated waveguide and the cavity out of the coupling region, (iv) maximize
 244 phononic and photonic modes confinement with high quality factors, in order to enhance their OM
 245 interaction. Comparison of the results obtained in the case of a cavity with uniform heights of the
 246 stubs has been also reported. Concerning the OM coupling coefficients, high coupling rates were
 247 found, up to 2 MHz, with photonic quality factor up to 10^7 for the parabolic cavity. Symmetry of
 248 the acoustic modes was **considered** in order to select only those that could couple with the confined
 249 photonic modes. Both moving interface and photoelastic contributions are included in the calculation
 250 of OM couplings. Finally, the numerical features of the performed simulations have been discussed to
 251 ensure repeatability of the analysis.

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 254 methodology, all Authors; software, A.G., D.M.; validation, A.G., D.M.; formal analysis, all Authors; investigation,
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261 Abbreviations

262 The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

263	OM	Opto-mechanical
	AO	Acousto-Optic
	PE	Photo-elastic
264	e.m.	electromagnetic
	MI	Moving Interface
	SS	Symmetric-Symmetric

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